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Smart Machines, Subtle Dangers: How Artificial Intelligence is Reshaping Academic Behaviour among University Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

¹Amarachukwu Ngozi Diekedie and ²Ifeoma Loveth Eze

^{1&2}Department of Sociology and Anthropology,
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

¹diekediean@fuotuoke.edu.ng, ORCID: 0009-0004-3803-5310 & ²ezeil@fuotuoke.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as ChatGPT, Perplexity, and Grammarly, among others, have increasingly demonstrated the extent to which machines can enhance teaching and learning activities. However, as these tools become increasingly integrated into academic life, concerns are emerging about their subtle impact on critical thinking, learning habits, and academic integrity among students. While existing literature has explored the benefits of AI in enhancing learning, very few studies have investigated the behavioural implications of AI dependency on students. Hence, this study examines how AI dependency is reshaping academic behaviour among university students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Using a survey approach, the study relies on data collected from 238 undergraduates across three universities in Bayelsa State. Participants were selected through a convenience approach that targeted four universities in the state. The data were gathered through the use of a virtual questionnaire instrument using Google forms shared to students' WhatsApp group platforms in all the universities. The analysis was done using descriptive statistics, particularly frequencies and percentages. Findings reveal an increasing dependence on AI tools for note preparation, assignments, and exam preparations at the expense of original thoughts and academic rigor. The study recommends the need for AI literacy and the promotion of ethical guidelines to govern how students engage with and use AI tools across Nigerian universities.

Keywords: Technology, AI dependency, undergraduates, academic behaviour, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Throughout human history, the wonder of man's ability to create ingenious scientific innovations remains a major defining character in the production and reproduction of human knowledge. Starting with the rudimentary technology associated with the Stone Age, which fundamentally redefined the way humans interacted with the physical environment, to the era of the printing press that provided the necessary revolutionary incentive for information dissemination, and of course, the digital revolution that gave birth to the knowledge economy (Castells, 2010), the evolutionary potentials of technology continue to propel human society, particularly how knowledge is dispensed. In other words, within each epoch of human progress, technology has not merely served as a support infrastructure for human capabilities but has almost always redefined the very fabric of how humans acquire, process, and apply knowledge.

In today's world, the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) stands out as a defining moment in the history of technological progress given its massive disruptive potentials and the associated promise of reshaping almost every sector, including education (Akinwalere & Inanov, 2022; Olatunji-Ishola, Onwuegbuzuie, & Okanlawon, 2025). Broadly defined as a computer-based system that is capable of

mimicking and performing tasks that typically require the intelligence of man, such as problem-solving, learning, and decision-making (Makanjuola-Agbola & Solomon, 2023), AI is progressively spreading its disruptive wings into educational systems globally. Hence, AI has become an integral part of teaching and learning resources as teachers and students now rely on it to complement various pedagogical techniques. This clearly comes with some potential benefits that ranges from personalized learning experience, automated managerial or administrative tasks, to enhanced research capabilities (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2019; Nwaokugha & Abiakwu, 2024). Beyond what teachers can do with AI, there is a growing understanding that platforms such as ChatGPT, Perplexity, Google Gemini, Microsoft Copilot, among others, can tailor contents to fit individual needs that can go a long way to promote improved academic outputs (Luckin et al., 2016; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

However, as AI machines become increasingly integrated into academic life, there are equally growing concerns about their subtle dangerous impacts on critical thinking, learning habits, and academic integrity, particularly amongst students of universities. From a consensus perspective, Neelakantan (2020) and Hwang et al. (2020) note that AI tools influence students' academic behaviour, learning, and development, with different degrees of challenges, impact, and feedbacks. However, while sounding a warning alarm, Qadir (2023) notes that students are likely to abuse these AI tools in carrying out their academic activities without considering ethical issues. Importantly, there is an increasing worry that AI is creating a dangerous trend of machine dependency amongst students who now rely solely on it for their class tests, take-home assignments, and examinations. This corroborates Vieriu and Petrea (2025) who emphasized the deteriorating state of the mind of students, due to consistent use of AI, noting that this erodes critical thinking, understanding, and human interaction, thereby increasing cases of academic theft and laziness. The ubiquitous nature of smart machines such as smartphones, pens, wristwatches, head phones, and eyeglasses, among others, makes it easy to access AI tools. Students' reliance on these portable technologies has contributed significantly to the increasing instances of academic dishonesty and intellectual fraud.

Although it is clear that the challenges that came with the wake of AI in the education sector can be considered as a global issue, their manifestations and complexities within the higher education system in Nigeria calls for specific empirical investigation. As would have been expected, several studies have examined the influence of AI on students' academic performance and awareness. For instance, the study by Okon, Ukpong, and Idiong (2024), which drew inference from one university in Nigeria, found that the use of AI tools has a positive correlation with academic performance. Furthermore, in a similar but broader study, Ngonso et al. (2025) found that majority of the students in the universities in Nigeria, use AI with positive implications for academic performance given its ability to simplify complex academic content. Despite the empirical consensus on the positive impact of AI on academic performance, these studies also highlight ethical concerns and the erosion of critical thinking as associated challenges. Interestingly, other studies have extended the issue of ethical challenges further by noting that students in Nigerian universities have used AI within a relatively little to no regulatory environment paving the way for massive copy and paste academic scenario (Sadiq, Bello, & Tukur, 2024; Izevbigie, Olajide, Olaniran, & Akintayo, 2025).

While we can argue that there is an expansive body of studies that have expanded our knowledge on how AI relates to academic performance on the one hand, and how it also undermines academic integrity due to mode of use on the other hand, very little has been done to delve into the behavioural shifts, such as changes in study habits, engagement with traditional learning resources, and problem-solving approaches, that are associated with increasing AI dependency among undergraduate students. This study examines how smart machines, in this case AI, present subtle dangers, particularly how these tools are reshaping academic behaviour among university students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Essentially, this study provides answers to three key questions;

- i. To what extent does the use of AI machines influence university students' study habits and their engagement with traditional learning resources in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?
- ii. How do undergraduate students perceive the impact of AI machines on their critical thinking abilities and academic integrity in universities in Bayelsa State?

- iii. Does the ease of using AI increase the likelihood of dependence on the machines by university students in Bayelsa State and what are the associated risks?

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework: How AI is linked to Changing Academic Behaviour

Figure 1 above captures the conceptual framework showing how the use of AI tools, referred to here as smart machines, is linked to the alterations in academic behaviour among students in selected universities in Bayelsa State. This change in academic behaviour of students is moderated or influenced by a mixture of perceived benefits and subtle risks that are associated with the tools. Hence, on one hand, AI tools such as ChatGPT, Google Gemini, Perplexity, and Grammarly present perceived benefits such as ease and efficiency in academic work. Perhaps this is why Alasmari et al. (2025) acknowledged the role of AI in personalizing learning, enhancing understanding, and scaling up academic performance among students. On the other hand, the figure highlights the existence of subtle dangers or risks, especially increased AI dependency, dwindling critical thinking, and high rate of academic misconduct. This resonates with Cook and Cook (2024) who, in their discussions on AI in management education note that the increasing integration of generative AI into academic activities raises major concerns that are linked to intellectual outsourcing as students continue to rely on smart machines than their own intellect. In the final analysis, the conceptual framework shows how benefits and risks combine to shape the academic behaviour of students, particularly study habits, problem-solving abilities, and academic honesty.

Literature Review

Artificial intelligence is said to have been used for the first time in a workshop in 1956 to explain “science and engineering of making intelligent machines, particularly intelligent computer programmes” (McCarthy et al., 2006). The massive proliferation of AI tools, which we have referred to here as ‘smart machines’, has brought about a transformative and we dare to say disruptive period for the education sector. The capabilities of AI in terms of text and video generation, as well as providing personalized feedback, has made these machines quite ubiquitous within the academic cycle, particularly for students. As Vieriu and Petrea (2025) note, AI has comprehensively transformed education with massive opportunities and threats for students’ development. This clearly shows the double-edged sword nature of AI integration into the education system, particularly when we consider the fact that it presents remarkable benefits while equally being a subtle source of danger that is currently reshaping how students behave towards learning in the universities.

The literature is tilted towards the recognition of the perceived benefits and transformative power of AI within the education sector, with several scholars drawing attention to the relative ease and efficiency associated with tools such as Google Gemini, ChatGPT, Perplexity, and Grammarly when it comes to the management of students' workload. In this regard, Acut et al. (2025) note that one key positive benefit that came with the integration of AI into academics is the fact that learning is now easily personalized, with AI being able to adapt to each individual's needs and enhance tailored understanding for such students (Ngonso, et al., 2025; Okafor, et al., 2025). Studies now show that students frequently make use of AI tools like ChatGPT for summarizing complex notes, writing their assignments, proofreading, or even writing their examinations, with significant improvement in their productivity and efficiency (Fuller & Barnes, 2024). This is evident as various institutions use algorithms such as Coursera and edX among others, to monitor the activities of students, analyse their performance, design curriculum, and process results (Melo, 2024; Vieriu & Petrea, 2025). It is believed that this level of efficiency introduced by AI into academics is a significant pointer to the fact that these tools are powerful enablers of academic work, since it has now fundamentally shaped the way students and teachers now approach tasks that were ordinarily time-intensive in the traditional sense (Adias, Raimi, & Adias, 2020; Gecker, 2025).

On the other side of the literature divide, you find scholars who have lent their voices to the argument about the growing AI dependency among students, with most of them believing that this portends some kind of 'subtle dangers' that now threatens the core values of academic integrity and intellectual progress in universities. These scholars are concerned about how AI dependency among students can effortlessly lead to a decline in students' critical thinking and problem-solving potentials. For instance, in one study, Yusuf, Pervin, & Romon-Gonzalez (2024) highlight the dangers of overdependence on AI, when they argued that this can lead to the erosion of academic integrity and critical thinking as students are now more likely than before to adopt machine driven information without any attempt to verify same. Similarly, Lye and Lim (2024) share the view that this emerging trend where students outsource their intellectual responsibilities to these machines presents huge risks of proliferating academic laziness, as students become more reliant on smart machines than their own brains to solve academic or even real-life problems. Additionally, the ease, pace, and efficiency with which AI platforms now generate coherent texts have increased concerns about academic fraud and plagiarism (Li, 2024; Zhai, Wibowo, & Li, 2024).

Based on the literature review presented above, it is easy to see that scholars are divided on the role of AI in higher education, particularly among students. While there are those who believe that AI has potentials to positively transform the academic behaviour of students and teachers alike, there those who profess the dangers associated with these machines. No matter the scholarly divide that we find ourselves, there is no doubting the fact that AI is a revolutionary technology that has the capability to be disruptive either positively or negatively when it comes to academic behaviour amongst students, particularly undergraduates in a developing country like Nigeria, where emerging technologies are operated within a less regulatory space (Owolabi et al., 2025).

Theoretical Framework

This study is theoretically guided by the Technological Determinism Theory, which is primarily associated with the American sociologist and economist Thorstein Veblen (1857–1929). This theory posits that technology does not assume the role of neutrality but comes with an inherent self-directed power that significantly shapes the norms of society with major impacts on cultural values, and by extension, human behaviours and lived realities. In the views of Veblen, the widespread adoption of technologies, particularly smart machines like AI tools, constitutes the very basis of the deterministic character of technology, with its ability to exert significant and irresistible influence on individuals in society. Locating this argument within the education system, it is easy to see that the theory assumes that the integration and proliferation of AI tools can go a long way to mold students' behaviour, actions, and thought processes, while determining how students conduct their academic activities. In our context, the overdependence or overreliance on AI means that these tools can readily interfere with the students' attitude towards their study.

One disturbing trend is the distractive outcome that AI now imposes as most students absent themselves from classes and pay little to no attention to their studies. This observable deviation in the learning values of students conforms with Drew's (2024) views when he noted that social structures and values are mostly determined by technologies, particularly as these machines progressively shape human ideologies. In other words, the theory's position that the use of technology has a significant impact on human actions and thoughts in society is strongly validated by Drew's submission above. For Veblen, the use of technology such as smart machines and AI tools, among others, is the basis for technological determinism. They have a strong influence and a close relationship with members of society. This relationship is perceived to exist among students in tertiary institutions including those in Bayelsa State and this is believed to be a dangerous trend if not controlled (Hallström, 2022), as students' ability to be creative, innovative, and constructive in their studies increasingly becomes limited (Doboli & Umbarkar, 2014; Akperi & Raimi, 2016).

Applied to our context, Veblen's theory guides the observation of a perceived AI dependency culture amongst students, which appears to have significant interference with the behaviour of students. The theory helps us to understand the manifestations of overdependence on AI by students in selected universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, particularly in light of associated behavioural shifts in academic activities. Thus, while the literature presents a robust regime of empirical evidence that supports the positive implications of AI use, the technological determinism theory provides a cautionary framework to guide the understanding that a subtle danger of increased intellectual passivity or shortcutting (Acut, 2025), lurks around the corner if care is not taken.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design that involved the use of a virtual questionnaire designed using Google Forms. The target population is comprised of undergraduate students across four universities (Federal University Otuoke, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa Medical University, and University of Africa) in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, from which 238 undergrads were drawn using the convenience sampling technique. This approach was preferred given the use of a virtual instrument to reach readily available students in their various WhatsApp groups. The virtual questionnaire was disseminated to the students' group platforms and the data filled were harvested and converted into excel spreadsheet for analysis. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically percentages and frequencies, which helped summarized the perceived impacts of AI on study habits and overall student's academic behaviour. However, for ethical reasons and for informed consent, students were pre-informed about the purpose of the study and assured of their anonymity and data confidentiality.

RESULTS

This section deals with the substantive data related to the research questions. Hence, the research questions are represented here and the relevant questionnaire items that relate to them are also presented to provide factual insight on each of the questions.

RQ1: *To what extent does the use of AI tools influence the study habits and engagement with traditional learning resources among university students in Bayelsa State?*

Figures 2 and 3 above provide data that directly address research question 1, which is targeted at understanding the extent to which AI machines influence the study habits of students and how they engage with traditional learning resources in the selected universities. Starting with Fig. 2, the data shows a significant shift in students’ engagement with traditional learning resources. When combined, the number of respondents (202/85%) who said they strongly agree and agree, shows that a significant number of them have slowed down in terms of reading course materials. This signifies a major adverse influence of AI on the study habit of the respondents as these tools now serve as substitutes for traditional course materials. On the other hand, a combined number of the respondents (36/15%) disagree and strongly disagree, suggesting that a small fraction of the respondents still read their course materials instead of relying solely on AI. Fig. 3 shows data on whether respondents rely on AI tools more than their own thinking for core assessment activities in their various schools. The data shows that there is a high level of dependence on AI amongst students when it comes to using the tools for their academic assessment activities. Drawing from the data, a total of 139 (58%) participants strongly agree and agree that they rely more on AI tools more than their own thinking for their course assessments. This shows that a good number of the respondents outsource their cognitive abilities to these machines when it comes to their academic tasks. Additionally, 99 (42%) of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree on the same issue. Still for the purpose of research question 1, the study tested for specific areas that students tend to use AI tools for their academic tasks.

Based on the data in Fig. 4, which highlights the purpose for which the study respondents mostly depend on AI tools for academic work, it is easy to see that a significant number (51%) of them deploy these tools for writing their assignments. This goes a long way to show that a good number of the students have high AI dependency when it comes to writing their assignments when compared with other areas of usage. Also, 28% of the respondents said they rely on AI machines for preparing for their exams, and this has implications for how students consolidate knowledge and revise their examination materials. 12% of the respondents said they use AI tools to help them in summarizing lecture notes, while 7% and 2% of them said that AI tools help them in areas such as proof-reading and grammar check, and in other areas. This data shows that AI is not a marginal tool when it comes to how students behave in relation to their academic activities.

RQ2: *How do undergraduate university students perceive the impact of AI machines on their critical thinking abilities and academic integrity in the selected schools?*

Figures 5 and 6 above provide data that relates to research question 2, which deals with how undergraduate students perceive the impact of AI machines on their critical thinking and academic integrity. Based on the data in Fig. 5, 163(69%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that AI machines help reduce their ability for critical thinking. This large number of respondents who show a

measure of self-awareness regarding the negative effect of AI dependence on their ability to think critically, shows that while students believe that AI brings some measure of convenience, it comes with a risk of thinking erosion. On the other hand, 75(31%) of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree on this issue. In the same vein, Fig. 6: measures students' perception on whether they feel that the use of AI for school work feels like cheating. The data in this regard shows that 109(46%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree to this, revealing that some of the students perceive the use of AI as cheating. However, a larger part of the sample 129(64%) believe that using AI does not amount to cheating on their part. This clearly shows that most of the students perceive their dependence on AI for their academic tasks as rather normal without any feeling of committing any academic fraud.

RQ3: *Does the ease of using AI increase the likelihood of dependence on the machines by university students in Bayelsa State and what are the associated risks?*

Figures 7 and 8 above address research question 3, which deals with the finding out the key factors that contribute to AI dependence among students in the selected university and also the perceived associated risks. Fig. 7 shows data on whether the ease of using AI tools for their academic tasks make students' more dependent on them. Drawing from the data, it is easy to see that a significant number (214/90%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that AI use makes their academic tasks easier and this drives dependence on the machines. This overwhelming number of students who see AI as simplifying their academic tasks suggest that ease of using these tools is a powerful incentive to continue to rely on AI for their routine academic works, thereby increasing the likelihood of continuous dependence. The smaller number of respondents (24(10%) who disagree and strongly disagree on this further deepens our understanding of the widespread acceptance of AI's relevance in making tasks easy for students. Fig. 8 on the other hand shows data on the perceived risks of AI dependence by students and the results show that 131(51%) of the students identify overdependence and laziness as the most prominent risk. Some of them (51/21%) see plagiarism or academic misconduct as the major risk that they face using AI machines, 35(15%) of the students see inaccurate or misleading content as the associated risks, 8(3%) of them are worried about data privacy, while 15(5%) of them said none of the above. The large number of respondents who see overdependence and laziness as the major risk associated with AI use goes a long way to show that most of the students are very much aware that AI dependency makes them lose their critical thinking skills.

FINDINGS

The first finding in this study is related to the influence of AI machines on the study habit or behaviour of students and their engagement with traditional learning resources. Hence, the findings show a significant influence of AI tools on the study behaviour or habits and engagement with traditional academic resources among the students. This is because, a good majority of the students reported a decline in their reading of traditional course materials since they started using AI. This trend shows that AI machines are progressively serving as substitutes for deep engagement with traditional textual documents and this highlights a significant shift in the study habits of the students. This strongly aligns with the technology determinism theory's assumption that the ease and convenience associated with smart machines such as AI tools, is actively reshaping the traditional practice of thorough reading, with a gradual shift to AI dependence rather than textual analysis (Cardonio, et al., 2025; Raimi & Boroh, 2025). This finding largely underscored the students' submission that there is a high level of AI dependence amongst them, particularly for their core academic assessment activities. This shows an increasing tendency for students to outsource their thinking abilities to AI machines, justifying the power of technology in shaping behaviours as reported by Drew (2024).

The second finding relates to research question two and it is concerned with finding out the perceived impact of AI machines on critical thinking abilities and academic integrity of students in the sampled universities. The results as presented in Figures 4 and 5 above shows that AI integration constitutes a subtle danger that undermines critical thinking and academic integrity as students become increasingly dependent on these tools for their routine academic activities. A good number of the respondents note that AI tools reduce their ability for critical thinking underscoring a major risk associated with the dependence on these machines. Furthermore, this finding points to the fact that even though the students perceive AI as offering them some kind of academic convenience, it also presents a trade-off scenario where ease of use comes at the expense of intellectual rigor, providing a strong justification for the Technology Determinism Theory's position that the influence of technology may bring about intellectual passivity (Acut et al., 2025). Additionally, the finding also reveals a mixed view on the perceived link between AI use and cheating in the universities. However, the fact that more of the participants see AI use as not constituting any form of academic fraud suggest that students are beginning to normalize the use of these tools, showcasing a significant influence on their academic behaviour.

With regard to research question three, which aimed to find out if the ease of using AI tools increases dependence among the students as well as the perceived risks of using the tools. The finding affirm that the perceived use of AI platforms is considered to be a significant driver of AI dependence and this points to a distinctive kind of risk. A significant percentage of the students confirmed that using AI tools makes their academic work a lot easier thereby increasing their dependence on these tools. This clearly acts as a serious incentive for students to sustain their reliance on AI for academic tasks supporting the finding of Okafor et al. (2025), who note that the inherent convenience associated with AI can increase the adoption level of these tools, while eroding academic integrity. This justifies the fact that students in this study identified overdependence and laziness as one of the most prominent risks associated with AI integration into their academic activities. Although, this self-awareness is vital in terms of students recognizing the direct consequence of AI overdependence, particularly its ability to diminish original intellectual efforts, they still consider this risk as worthwhile given the convenience they derive from using AI to address academic tasks. While other risks such as plagiarism or academic misconduct and misleading content were also highlighted, the subtle danger lies more on the erosion of critical thinking among university students.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that the use of AI by university undergraduate students in Bayelsa state presents some key concerns that represent subtle dangers that now threaten academic integrity and critical thinking ability. Therefore, it has shown how AI use is actively increasing the dependence on such machines for academic tasks among students thereby reshaping the academic behaviour of these students. This is because, it clearly established a consistent shift in the study habit of the students, given the progressive

reduction in how these students engage traditional learning resources and the increasing reliance on AI for key academic tasks, such as study habits related to exam preparation habits, assignment completion, and note summarization. The study concludes therefore, that although participants believe that the ease and efficiency that AI tools have introduced into their academic works is considered to be beneficial, this convenience comes with some major risks. Primary among these risks is the increasing overdependence on AI machines for completing academic tasks and this equally promotes erosion of critical thinking among the students. This leads to the central submission of this study that AI is not just an auxiliary machine but a transformative platform that is now influencing students' academic behaviour and this requires proactive strategies to promote responsible use within the university system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the findings and conclusion reached in this study, the following suggestions have been proffered to help facilitate responsible AI integration for undergraduate students in universities.

- i. There is need for the various universities to develop and implement a comprehensive AI literacy and mainstreaming programme. The programmes should be targeted at covering the functionalities of the various AI tools and more importantly, how AI can be integrated into undergraduate academic activities responsibly or ethically. The suggested programme should also highlight the need to evaluate AI generated content and also educate students on the risks of overdependence on these tools.
- ii. Also, the various universities' management team should facilitate the establishment and communication of AI integration ethical guidelines. Given the effect of AI use on academic integrity, there is need for universities to develop and disseminate unambiguous policies and guidelines for the use of these tools by students, particularly for the purposes of assignments, examinations, and other related researches. These guidelines should also come with a mechanism for strict enforcement to ensure that students comply with them.
- iii. There is need for innovative teaching and learning activities in the universities as a way of counteracting the observed decline in the use of traditional learning resources and the overdependence on AI for academic tasks. In this sense, lecturers should be innovative by creating assignments and examinations that require higher-level thinking, originality, and critical analysis that AI tools may not easily replicate. On the other hand, lecturers may choose to design assessments that require students to use AI responsibly or ethically without necessarily seeing these tools as substitutes for their independent thought.

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